

SVMSMOTE-ENC: A Novel Oversampling Method for Imbalanced Datasets with Nominal and Continuous Features

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Abstract. Class imbalance is one of the most challenging problems for machine learning algorithms. The most commonly used classification algorithms also suffer from the curse of highly imbalanced data. Numerous methods have been proposed in the literature to address the class imbalance problem; however, many of these approaches are complex and often introduce unnecessary noise into the data. Moreover, effective oversampling techniques that can handle datasets containing both nominal and continuous features remain limited. Although SMOTE-ENC (SMOTE for Encoded Nominal and Continuous features) can capture the relationship between categorical features and the target variable, it does not explicitly enforce the decision boundary. To address these challenges, we propose a new oversampling approach, SVMSMOTE-ENC, for nominal and continuous features, based on a combination of a Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier and SMOTE-ENC. Our method modifies the encoding mechanism of SMOTE-ENC and replaces its random selection of observations with a targeted selection of more informative minority class instances. An SVM classifier is trained to find the borderline between the minority and the majority classes and synthetic minority samples are generated around the SVM decision boundary. Our approach was evaluated on six standard imbalanced datasets, and the performance of SVMSMOTE-ENC was compared with SMOTE-NC and two state-of-the-art oversampling methods. The experimental results show that our proposed method provides better performance in terms of F1-score and balanced accuracy.

Keywords: Imbalanced classification, class imbalance, oversampling methods, minority class, synthetic samples, comparative analysis, evaluation methodologies, Support Vector Machine, SMOTE-ENC, SMOTE-NC, G-SMOTENC

1 Introduction

Class imbalance poses a significant challenge in classification tasks, particularly when aiming to achieve accurate predictions for minority class data points. Methods for dealing with imbalanced data can be categorized into three main groups: algorithm-level, ensemble learning, and data-level. Algorithm-level methods aim to modify the existing algorithms or design new ones to better handle imbalanced data during model training. These approaches adjust the loss function by assigning a higher weight to the misclassification of samples associated with the minority classes. One of the most widely used algorithm-level techniques is cost-sensitive learning, which assigns a high cost to misclassification of the minority class, and trying to minimize the overall cost. Algorithm-level methods are often problem-specific. The appropriate misclassification costs can vary depending on the specific dataset and problem. In many real-world scenarios, it's not always clear what the exact cost of misclassifying a class is. It has been shown through empirical results and theoretical analysis that mislabeled training examples can pose serious challenges for cost-sensitive classification, especially when misclassifying certain classes is extremely expensive [1]. Ensemble learning approaches differ from traditional single-classification models by combining multiple base models into a unified, stronger model. Among ensemble-based methods, bagging and boosting are the most commonly used approaches. The success of an ensemble method depends on several factors, including how the baseline models are trained and how they are combined. In contrast, data-level methods address class imbalance by rebalancing the class distribution before classification, aiming to reduce the impact of skewed class distributions on the learning process [2]. These techniques include oversampling,

which increases the number of instances in the underrepresented class, undersampling, which reduces the number of instances in the overrepresented class, and hybrid method that combines both [3]. Resampling techniques for imbalanced data offer key advantages, particularly in their independence from the specific underlying classifier, providing a versatile solution applicable across various machine learning algorithms. Empirical evidence supports the effectiveness of applying a preprocessing step to balance the class distribution. Undersampling involves the removal of training instances, which may result in the loss of informative samples. When minority class observations are small, balancing via undersampling can result in an excessively small training set, potentially reducing classification performance.

Random oversampling is the simplest form of oversampling aiming to balance class distribution by randomly duplicating instances from the minority class. However, researchers [4] caution that the straightforward duplication of minority class instances makes it more susceptible to overfitting. Consequently, classifiers might create rules that seem accurate but are, in reality, based on duplicated examples. Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) is quite popular among oversampling techniques [5, 6]. However, SMOTE algorithm also has its limitations when dealing with datasets containing categorical (nominal) and features, the traditional SMOTE method cannot be directly applicable. Noise sensitivity is another limitation of SMOTE, as it can amplify existing noise in the data, especially when generating synthetic samples from noisy minority instances among the majority class instances. Since classification algorithms tend to be more affected by noise than by class imbalance [7], different overfitting management techniques like pruning in decision trees are often used to mitigate overfitting. However, by using such strategies, correct clusters of minority class examples may be ignored [8].

Cluster-based SMOTE first applies K-means clustering to the minority class examples to identify localized regions. SMOTE is then applied within each cluster to generate synthetic examples. By generating synthetic examples within each minority cluster, the method targets specific local regions rather than the entire dataset at once. This focused, localized approach helps the model better learn the characteristics of the minority class and improves SMOTE's effectiveness on imbalanced datasets [9]. Safe-Level SMOTE assigns each positive instance a safe level ratio based on the number of positive neighbors it has and generates synthetic samples closer to the instances with the highest safe levels. SMOTE may generate synthetic instances in unsuitable locations, such as overlapping or noisy regions. In contrast, generating synthetic instances in safe positions by considering the number of minority class instances in the neighborhood can improve the prediction performance of classifiers [10].

While traditional techniques, like SMOTE, rely on linear interpolation of minority class examples to generate synthetic data, deep generative models are now emerging as a promising alternative. These models have a greater capacity to capture complex data distributions and generate more realistic synthetic instances. Despite their promise, these models still struggle with effectively addressing class imbalance during training [11].

Douzas et al. [12] introduced Geometric SMOTE (G-SMOTE) as an enhancement of the standard SMOTE data generation technique. To generate a synthetic sample, G-SMOTE first selects a minority instance at random and identifies one of its nearest neighbors in the training set. The distance between these two instances is used to define the radius of a hyperspherical region centered on the selected instance. A synthetic sample is then generated at random within this region, and the process is repeated until the desired number of synthetic samples is obtained. Unlike SMOTE, which interpolates linearly between minority instances, G-SMOTE generates synthetic samples within a geometric region in the input space centered on each selected minority instance. By default, this region is a hypersphere, but G-SMOTE allows it to deform into a hyperellipsoid, enabling the oversampling process to adapt to the

specific structure of the minority distribution. This flexibility effectively parameterizes the data generation process, making it more suitable for the characteristics of each imbalanced dataset. Nevertheless, if the minority class contains noisy or outlier samples, G-SMOTE may produce unrealistic synthetic points around them, potentially degrading classifier performance.

Real-world datasets typically contain both numerical and categorical features; therefore, conventional SMOTE is not directly applicable to such mixed-type data. To address this issue, Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique for Nominal and Continuous features, SMOTE-NC [6], has been proposed and widely adopted in mixed-feature settings. However, this oversampling method tends to generate unnecessary noise. SMOTE-NC incorporates the median of the standard deviations of continuous features within the minority class when computing distances. Therefore, SMOTE-NC is not designed to work only with categorical features; it requires at least one continuous feature. Geometric SMOTE for nominal and continuous features, G-SMOTENC [13], is based on a combination of G-SMOTE and SMOTE-NC. It first generates continuous features using G-SMOTE's generation mechanism and then assigns categorical features by taking the mode of the nearest neighbors, so it is not designed to work with only categorical features and requires some numerical features.

Most imbalanced classification methods based on resampling techniques rely heavily on SMOTE. However, they inherit the limitations of SMOTE, such as sensitivity to noisy points and overgeneralization. To address the aforementioned issues, a new approach is proposed to improve the decision boundary through the generation of effective synthetic samples. Categorical variables were encoded based on the strength of association between each category and the minority class. A Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier is trained to estimate the borderline area that guide our proposed oversampler in generating minority class instances.

2 Related Work

In this section, we summarize the algorithms and research work related to this study. Oversampling using SMOTE mitigates overfitting by avoiding the exact replication of instances [6]. To create new samples, SMOTE randomly selects minority class instances from the dataset. New instances are created via linear interpolation between these minority samples and their k -nearest minority neighbors (commonly $k = 5$). Nevertheless, the original SMOTE faces significant limitations for datasets containing categorical features, as the algorithm generates synthetic samples through interpolation in continuous feature space, which cannot be directly applied to nominal variables. Regions with high concentrations of minority samples are more likely to be further amplified, whereas sparse minority areas remain underrepresented, as reported in prior studies [14,15].

In SMOTE-NC, the median of the standard deviations of continuous features within the minority class is computed and incorporated into the distance metric. When selecting nearest-neighbor, this value is added to the Euclidean distance if discrepancies in nominal features are present, thereby penalizing categorical mismatches based on the typical variability of continuous attributes. However, SMOTE-NC struggles with multi-label nominal features, as it cannot capture how each label relates to the minority class. In SMOTE-NC, all mismatches in categorical features are treated equally in the distance calculation. For each categorical attribute, the contribution to the distance is 0 if the values match and the median of the standard deviations of continuous features within the minority class if they differ, regardless of the specific categories involved. It also requires at least one continuous feature, which limits its applicability for datasets containing only categorical attributes.

2.1 SMOTE-ENC (SMOTE—Encoded Nominal and Continuous)

M. Mukherjee and M. Khushi [16] introduced SMOTE-ENC to generate synthetic data for nominal and continuous features, employing an encoding mechanism derived from Pearson’s Chi-squared test. The Chi-based contribution of each category c_i with respect to the minority class j was then computed as:

$$\chi(c_{ij}) = \frac{O_{ij} - E_{ij}}{E_{ij}},$$

where O_{ij} denotes the total number of observations falling into each combination of category c_i and minority target class y_j , and E_{ij} represents the expected number for category c_i associated with the minority class y_j . The Chi-based contribution represents the proportional deviation of the observed frequency from the expected frequency of each category with respect to the minority class. A higher value of $\chi(\cdot)$ reflects a stronger relationship with the minority class and highlights category that carries greater informative value. SMOTE-ENC combines the encoded training dataset with newly generated samples, and then converts the data back to its original representation. To do this, each category must be mapped to a unique encoded value. However, this approach does not guarantee the uniqueness of the encoded values. Although SMOTE-ENC reduces the complexity introduced by categorical variables by fusing categories that exhibit the same amount of association with the minority class, the category collapsing is applied only to the training set. Moreover, the SMOTE-ENC algorithm does not explicitly enforce the decision boundary. Instances located far from the class border receive the same oversampling probability as those positioned closer to the boundary. Research suggests that classifiers might derive advantages from generating samples nearer to the class border [17]. Another major concern is that SMOTE-ENC may further amplify noise present in the data. This is likely to happen when majority vote of the noisy minority data and its k nearest neighbors leading to the generation of synthetic samples that resemble the majority class rather than the minority class.

2.2 Support Vector Machine

A Support Vector Machine (SVM) addresses classification problems by finding the hyperplane that maximizes the separation between data points of different classes. When the classes are not linearly separable, SVM uses the “kernel trick”, which involves mapping the data into a higher-dimensional space where a linear boundary can be found. This method enables SVM to handle complex and high-dimensional datasets effectively, as noted by Cortes and Vapnik [18]. One of the key strengths of SVM is its robustness and ability to avoid overfitting, particularly when the classes are clearly separable. Its consistency is further enhanced by the use of various kernel functions, such as the Radial Basis Function (RBF) and polynomial kernels. This adaptability makes SVM a popular choice for a wide range of applications, from bioinformatics to text analysis.

2.3 Support Vector Machine SMOTE

Support Vector Machine SMOTE (SVMSMOTE) [19] addresses class imbalance by generating synthetic minority samples specifically along the decision boundary, as presented in the following steps. Let the support vector set be SV , consisting of a positive (minority) subset $SV^+ \subset S$ and a negative (majority) subset. For each minority instance $SV_i^+ \in SV^+$, SVM-SMOTE identifies its m nearest neighbors from the entire support vector set. Let m' denote the number of majority samples among these neighbors.

- If $m' = m$, the instance SV_i^+ is regarded as noise and excluded from oversampling.
- If $0 \leq m' < m/2$, SV_i^+ is considered safe.
- Otherwise, SV_i^+ is labeled as in danger.

In the next stage, new samples will be generated based on their labels.

For SV_i^+ labeled as danger, new samples are generated using linear interpolation between the danger sample SV_i^+ and one of its m nearest neighbors, chosen at random:

$$x_{\text{new}}^+ = sv_i^+ + \omega(sv_i^+ - x_{\text{nn}})$$

where x_{nn} is one of the positive nearest neighbor of SV_i^+ ; ω is a random number in the range $[0, 1]$.

Otherwise, for a safe sample SV_i^+ , new samples are generated via linear extrapolation:

$$x_{\text{new}}^+ = sv_i^+ + \omega(x_{\text{nn}} - sv_i^+)$$

The generation parameter ω enables the positive data to expand into areas with few negative samples. This expansion helps refine the decision boundary.

3 Proposed Method

In many imbalanced datasets, the decision boundary is dominated by the majority class, resulting in a classifier biased toward the majority class. Consequently, minority samples are often misclassified, and using standard machine learning classifiers on such datasets reduces predictive performance on the minority classes. In this study, we present a novel oversampling approach that integrates an SVM classifier to identify and target regions where synthetic data generation is most effective. The proposed SVMSMOTE-ENC method differentiates itself from traditional oversampling methods such as SMOTE-NC and SMOTE-ENC through its unique combination of SVM classifier and synthetic sample generation. While traditional SMOTE-ENC generates synthetic samples through interpolation of numerical features and majority-based assignment of categorical features, SVMSMOTE-ENC incorporates an additional boundary identification stage prior to oversampling. In SVMSMOTE-ENC, the continuous part of the newly generated instances is created by interpolating along the line connecting a randomly selected minority class support vector with its nearest minority neighbors, while the categorical part is assigned using the most frequent category among the nearest neighbors, like SMOTE-ENC. As a result, SVMSMOTE-ENC diminishes the probability of generating noisy or unrealistic samples by avoiding interpolation across arbitrary minority instances.

We modify the encoding mechanism of SMOTE-ENC to map each categorical level to a unique value, thereby guaranteeing a unique representation for each category. Specific steps of the modified encoding method are described in Algorithm 1. The Chie-based encoding captures the relationship between categorical features and the target variable, potentially improving model performance. However, in SMOTE-ENC, the samples selected for oversampling are not chosen selectively, meaning that noisy and less informative instances may also be oversampled.

Algorithm 1: SVMSMOTE-ENC's encoding mechanism

Input:

Xcat: Subset of the dataset containing only the categorical columns
y: Target variable
minority_class : Label of the minority class
n_continuous: Number of continuous variables in the dataset
median_sd: Median of standard deviation of continuous features (if any)

Output:

Xcat_encoded: Encoded categorical features
encoded_list: List of dictionaries containing categories and their corresponding encoded values (one dictionary per feature)

Function CatEncoder(Xcat , y, minority_class):

```
encoded_list ← empty list
for each feature F in Xcat do
  i ← 1
  encoded_dict ← empty dictionary
  for each category c in unique values of F do
     $\chi(c) \leftarrow$  Compute the category's Chi-based contribution rounded to 4 decimal places
    if n_continuous > 0 then
       $\chi^*(c) \leftarrow \chi(c) \times m$ 
    else
       $\chi^*(c) \leftarrow \chi(c)$ 
    end if
    // Ensure unique encoding for each category
    if  $\chi^*(c)$  in values(encoded_dict) then
       $\chi^*(c) \leftarrow \chi^*(c) + i \times 1e-5$ 
      i ← i + 1
    end if
    encoded_dict[c] ←  $\chi^*(c)$ 
    Replace each value in feature F with its corresponding encoded value
  end for
  Add encoded_dict to encoded_list
end for
#Return the encoded categorical features along with the list of encoding mappings
return Xcat_encoded, encoded_list
```

In this paper, we focus on oversampling method that uses a support vector machine as a decision-boundary estimator to deal with the imbalanced data. Once borderline areas are identified, the filtering phase begins. In the filtering process, noisy support vectors are identified, preventing oversampling in unsafe regions. In the oversampling phase of the algorithm, the modified SMOTE-ENC is used to populate borderline areas. The proposed method helps expand the minority class to the areas where the density of majority class instances is not so high. SVMSMOTE-ENC targets minority class instances that are difficult to classify, typically located at the borderline between the minority class and the majority class of the dataset, obtained after training a standard SVM classifier on the original training set. The pseudo-code of our proposed method is presented in Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2: SVMSMOTE-ENC

Input: X: Training dataset

y: Target variable

n: Total number of synthetic samples to be generated

k_neighbors: Number of nearest neighbors for synthetic samples generation

m_neighbors: Number of nearest neighbors used to choose the sampling strategy (interpolation or extrapolation)

Output: Resampled dataset ($X_{\text{resampled}}, Y_{\text{resampled}}$)

1: Apply Chi-based encoding

Encode the categorical features in the training set as discussed in Algorithm 1, denoted as $X_{\text{chi_encoded}}$

2: Identify borderline area

2.1: Train a standard SVM classifier on the One-hot encoded training set and extract the support index.

2.2: Get the encoded support vectors based on Algorithm 1

2.3: Filter positive class support vectors, denoted as SV^+

3: Determine danger and safe support vectors

For each support vector sv_i^+ in SV^+ , m nearest neighbors are identified from the entire Support vector set. Each sv_i^+ is then labeled as noisy, safe, or in danger, as described in section 2

4: Oversampling steps

4.1: Generate new samples based on label categorie

-Apply extrapolation to the numerical features of the support vectors marked as safe:

$$x_{\text{new}}^+ = sv_i^+ + \omega(sv_i^+ - x_{\text{nn}}),$$

where x_{nn} is the positive nearest neighbor of sv_i^+ ; ω is a random number in the range $[0, 1]$.

-Apply interpolation to the numerical features of the support vectors classified as in danger

$$x_{\text{new}}^+ = sv_i^+ + \omega(x_{\text{nn}} - sv_i^+)$$

4.2: Perform a majority-based assignment for categorical attributes

Each categorical feature takes the majority value among its nearest neighbors

4.3: Combine new samples to original samples (Chi-based encoded)

$$X_{\text{resampled}} = X_{\text{chi_encoded}} \cup X_{\text{new}}$$

4.4: Convert the data back to its original form

4.5: Assign new labels to $Y_{\text{resampled}}$

4.6: Return: ($X_{\text{resampled}}, Y_{\text{resampled}}$)

The proposed method generates synthetic instances using a more targeted approach that better preserves feature relationships. To enhance learning near the class boundary, synthetic minority samples are generated to populate the decision boundary. Our method interpolates only borderline instances, where misclassification is most likely. These instances are identified using the support vectors. Focusing on borderline samples provides the classifier with more informative minority examples, which reduces misclassification error. The amplification of noise should be reduced by detecting noisy support vectors.

4 Experiments on Real-World Datasets

To evaluate our work, the well-known Random Forest (RF) classifier is employed and trained on oversampled data. The extracted findings are supported by statistical comparative analysis

on six datasets. The proposed method is tailored to binary classification, but it can be extended to multi-class problems, where additional considerations regarding classification and evaluation need to be addressed, as discussed by Fernández et al. [20].

4.1 Random Forest Classifier

Random Forest is an ensemble learning algorithm that combines multiple independent Decision Trees to improve prediction accuracy and reduce overfitting. It uses bootstrapping (sampling with replacement) to create different subsets of the training data for each tree. Additionally, a random feature selection process is used for each tree. The final prediction is made by aggregating the results of all trees—through majority voting for classification tasks or averaging for regression tasks. We used the scikit-learn library, which includes an implementation of the RF classifier. In our experiments, the following hyperparameters are used for RF: `max_features='log2'`, `n_estimators=500`, `criterion='gini'`, `min_samples_leaf=10`, and `max_depth={5,8}`.

4.2 Datasets

We conducted experiments on six well known datasets from the UCI machine learning repository and Kaggle including Banking Telemarketing, Insurance, Tic-Tac-Toe, and German and Australian Credit data.

4.2.1 Banking Telemarketing Dataset

The Bank Telemarketing dataset contains real-world telemarketing records collected from a Portuguese retail bank, aimed at promoting long-term deposits. It was published on the UCI repository [21]. Each contact outcome is encoded as a binary variable indicating success or failure. In addition to outbound calls, inbound contacts are considered, where clients contacting the call center for other purposes may be offered the deposit. A stratified 20% subsample of the dataset was utilized in this study. During the data preprocessing phase, outliers and records with missing values were removed. Outliers were detected using a Z-score threshold of $|Z| > 3.5$. This procedure helps prevent extreme values from adversely influencing the analysis or degrading the performance of the model. To reduce multicollinearity, the variables `emp.var.rate` and `nr.employed` were excluded from the feature set. Although the duration attribute shows a strong correlation with the target variable and could potentially improve predictive performance, it was removed because call duration is not available prior to initiating a client contact. Excluding this variable prevents information leakage and enhances the model's ability to generalize to unseen data.

4.2.2 Insurance Dataset

The insurance dataset ¹ was obtained from an insurance company providing health insurance products. It contains historical records of policyholders, including demographic information, insurance-related attributes, and customer response variables. The data were used to construct a supervised learning task aimed at predicting whether existing health insurance customers would purchase vehicle insurance offered by the same provider. Prior to model development, standard preprocessing steps were applied to ensure data quality and suitability for machine learning analysis. This dataset was originally provided with predefined training and test splits, both exhibiting a similar level of class imbalance. Since our evaluation is based on nested cross-validation, we decided to combine them so that the resulted dataset can be split again later. For this study, a stratified subsample of the combined dataset, consisting of 12,892 records, was

¹ <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/arashnic/imbalanced-data-practice/data>

selected. Stratified sampling ensures that the class proportions in the subsample reflect those of the full dataset, which helps maintain representativeness and reduces potential sampling bias.

4.2.3 German Credit Dataset

The German Credit dataset, containing observations for 1000 applicants for credit, was obtained from the UCI repository [22]. Each instance is labeled according to creditworthiness, with the class attribute indicating either good (1) or bad (2) credit. The classification task is to predict whether an individual presents a good or bad credit risk.

4.2.4 Australian Credit Approval Dataset

The Australian Credit dataset [23] contains 690 credit card application records, labeled to indicate whether a credit application is approved (1) or denied (0). The dataset is relatively balanced, with approximately 55% approvals and 45% denials. To protect personal information, all attributes are anonymized and labeled with letter codes, including six numerical and eight categorical features.

4.2.5 Tic-Tac-Toe Endgame Dataset

The Tic-Tac-Toe Endgame dataset from the UCI repository [24] contains all possible end-board configurations for the game Tic-Tac-Toe, with the goal of determining whether player “X” won or not. The dataset is deterministic and includes exactly eight distinct ways that player “X” can win, each one of the 8 ways to get 3 “X”s in a row on a 3×3 grid.

4.2.6 Breast Cancer Dataset

The Breast Cancer dataset [25] describes patient characteristics and tumor properties collected at the University Medical Centre, Institute of Oncology, Ljubljana, Yugoslavia. The binary target variable indicates whether a patient experienced no recurrence events or recurrence events. The features are discretized, and we removed instances with missing or duplicate values prior to analysis.

Table 1. Summary of datasets

Dataset	Size	#Nom.	#Cont.	#Positive class	#Negative class	IR
Bank	11260	11	5	1248	10012	0.11
Insurance	12892	6	4	2112	10780	0.16
German Credit	1000	13	7	300	700	0.3
Australian Credit	690	8	6	307	383	0.45
Tic-Tac-Toe	958	9	0	332	626	0.35
Breast Cancer	255	9	0	71	184	0.28

Size: Total samples; #Nom./#Cont.: Number of nominal/continuous features; #Positive/#Negative class: Number of minority/majority instances; IR: Imbalance ratio ($IR = \#Positive\ class / Size$)

After applying the data cleaning and feature selection steps described above, the resulting dataset statistics are summarized in Table 1. The imbalance ratio (IR) is defined as the number of minority instances divided by the total number of instances in the dataset. The datasets exhibit different imbalance ratios, offering a broad range for testing the efficiency of the proposed algorithm. Initially, the datasets were manually preprocessed to remove features and observations containing missing values. Subsequently, preprocessing was performed within a pipeline, where feature scaling and resampling were applied prior to model training to prevent data leakage and ensure consistent and reproducible model training.

To ensure unbiased model selection and reliable performance estimation, nested cross-validation was employed. A stratified 4-fold external loop was adopted for model performance estimation, while an internal 3-fold loop was applied for hyperparameter tuning. The outer loop was repeated five times over different random seeds, resulting in 60 inner training-validation pairs per model. The minority class was oversampled to the level at which both classes attained equal sizes. To avoid over-optimism problem, only the training set is oversampled [26]. Stratification ensures that the imbalance ratio in the training set is consistent with the original dataset. In each repetition of the outer loop, the dataset was divided into four equally sized folds while preserving the original class distribution. In each of the four iterations, one fold served as the test set, and the remaining three folds were used for model training and parameter tuning. For each dataset, we select the results of the hyperparameters that optimize the performance of a resampler/classifier. The results are reported as the average of 20 experimental runs for each dataset. In addition to the mean score, the standard deviation is reported to investigate the robustness of the models.

We implement our method using python programming language. The comparison of SVMSMOTE-ENC with the benchmark models was set under similar conditions, allowing each model to explore different hyperparameter combinations. The best hyperparameters were selected from the following predefined ranges:

- SMOTE-ENC/ SMOTE-NC
 $k_neighbors \in \{3, 5\}$
- SVM SMOTE-ENC
 $k_neighbors \in \{3, 5\}$
 $m_neighbors \in \{8, 10\}$
- G-SMOTENC
 $k_neighbors \in \{3, 5\}$
 $truncation_factor \in \{0.2, 0.5, 1\}$
 $deformation_factor \in \{0.5, 0.75\}$

In order to evaluate the effectiveness of our proposed oversampler, SVMSMOTE-ENC's performance is compared against three benchmark methods: SMOTE-NC's and two other state-of-the-art oversampling methods, SMOTE-ENC and G-SMOTENC. The non-parametric Wilcoxon signed-rank test [27] was conducted to perform pairwise comparisons among the proposed model and three other oversampling methods on six imbalanced datasets. The statistical test was performed on F1-score and balanced accuracy. A p-value threshold of 0.05 was used to determine whether the results were statistically significant. We consider our approach to be statistically significant, as the p-value from the Wilcoxon signed-rank test was less than 0.05 for both the F1-score and balanced accuracy.

5 Results and Discussion

In this section, we present the experimental results. Our focus is on comparing classification performance when using oversampling methods whose generation mechanisms are compatible with datasets containing both nominal and continuous features. The analysis was conducted in two stages. First, the average results over all folds and repetitions were reported, highlighting the best results in bold, followed by a discussion of the main insights derived from the experimental analysis. The experiments were run in Python 3.13.5 on a 64-bit Windows 11

system with Intel (R) Core(TM) i5-8250U CPU @ 1.60GHz, 1800 Mhz, 4 Core(s), 8 Logical Processor(s) and 8 GB of RAM. Tables 2 shows the performance of Random Forest classifier using data oversampled with SVMSMOTE-ENC, compared to benchmark methods.

Table 2. Table showing the mean and standard deviation of balanced accuracy and F1-score across multiple datasets, folds, and runs for several oversampling strategies.

Dataset	Resampler	Balanced_acc	F1-score
Bank	SVMSMOTE-ENC	0.7351 ± 0.009	0.7020 ± 0.011
Bank	G-SMOTENC	0.7057 ± 0.015	0.7003 ± 0.010
Bank	SMOTE-ENC	0.7316 ± 0.015	0.6786 ± 0.022
Bank	SMOTE-NC	0.7281 ± 0.013	0.6785 ± 0.022
Insurance	SVMSMOTE-ENC	0.8249 ± 0.006	0.7167 ± 0.007
Insurance	G-SMOTENC	0.8233 ± 0.005	0.6898 ± 0.005
Insurance	SMOTE-ENC	0.8238 ± 0.006	0.6910 ± 0.011
Insurance	SMOTE-NC	0.8240 ± 0.004	0.6900 ± 0.012
German Credit	SVMSMOTE-ENC	0.7128 ± 0.031	0.7051 ± 0.032
German Credit	G-SMOTENC	0.7080 ± 0.035	0.6966 ± 0.035
German Credit	SMOTE-ENC	0.7100 ± 0.022	0.6975 ± 0.022
German Credit	SMOTE-NC	0.7015 ± 0.034	0.6918 ± 0.029
Australian Credit	SVMSMOTE-ENC	0.8772 ± 0.018	0.8720 ± 0.018
Australian Credit	G-SMOTENC	0.8686 ± 0.044	0.8687 ± 0.044
Australian Credit	SMOTE-ENC	0.8707 ± 0.030	0.8680 ± 0.028
Australian Credit	SMOTE-NC	0.8697 ± 0.023	0.8679 ± 0.024
Tic-Tac-Toe	SVMSMOTE-ENC	0.8543 ± 0.029	0.8624 ± 0.031
Tic-Tac-Toe	SMOTE-ENC	0.8384 ± 0.029	0.8455 ± 0.030
Breast Cancer	SVMSMOTE-ENC	0.6631 ± 0.0681	0.6712 ± 0.0687
Breast Cancer	SMOTE-ENC	0.6352 ± 0.0442	0.6451 ± 0.0441

As shown in Table 2, two main findings can be identified. First, across the six datasets, SVMSMOTE-ENC achieved the best performance among the evaluated methods in terms of F1-score and balanced accuracy. Second, the biggest F1-score gain was achieved by the proposed oversampler on Insurance dataset (3.87%), with a significant gain also observed on bank dataset (3.46%), relative to SMOTE-NC. It was observed that G-SMOTENC was the most time-consuming oversampling method, which limits its practical applicability. At a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$, all pairwise comparisons reject the null hypothesis of no significant difference among the investigated methods, indicating that SVMSMOTE-ENC is statistically superior to other oversampling approaches in three out of six datasets. The Wilcoxon signed-rank test yields p-values below 0.05 for all comparisons, confirming that the improvements achieved by SVMSMOTE-ENC are statistically significant. Additionally, contrary to the results reported in [16], no significant improvement was observed for SMOTE-ENC relative to the baseline SMOTE-NC. The performance improvement of SVMSMOTE-ENC comes from the fact that it carefully and effectively generates minority samples. The most significant improvements are observed with datasets having low degree of overlap, due to the ability of expanding area.

Evaluation on Bank and Insurance Datasets

Among the four oversampling methods, the proposed method achieved the highest mean F1-score and balanced accuracy. The statistical significance of the improvement over three oversamplers in our experiment was confirmed using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test ($p < 0.04$) for F1-score and balanced accuracy. Training G-SMOTENC is a time-consuming process. On

the Insurance dataset, both SMOTE-ENC and SMOTE-NC achieved higher average balanced accuracy than G-SMOTENC.

Additionally, the impact of the proposed oversampler on feature importance was evaluated using the bank and insurance datasets, highlighting differences between the proposed and benchmark model SMOTE-ENC after oversampling.

Figure 1. Feature importance results from a Random Forest classifier trained with SVMSMOTE-ENC on the bank dataset.

Figure 2. Feature importance results from a Random Forest classifier trained with SMOTE-ENC on the bank dataset.

The top 10 feature importances of the proposed model and the SMOTE-ENC baseline model using the bank dataset were further compared, as illustrated in Figs. 1 and 2. Several categorical features were ranked among the top 10 predictors in both models, with only minor variations in their relative importance. Macroeconomic indicators, including euribor3m, cons.conf.idx, and cons.price.idx, were among the most influential features in both models. The contribution of these continuous variables was higher in the proposed model ($\approx 65\%$) compared to the baseline ($\approx 55\%$), indicating an increased reliance on macroeconomic continuous features. Minor variations in ranking were observed among mid-ranked features, such as month, campaign, and pdays_c. A single discrepancy was identified at the lower end of the ranking, where default in the proposed model was replaced by job in the baseline model. Despite the overall similarity in feature importance, a statistically significant improvement in F1-score was achieved by the proposed model. This improvement can be attributed to enhanced sample generation, improved decision boundaries, and the increased contribution of continuous features, rather than substantial changes in feature ranking.

Figure 3. Feature importance results from a Random Forest classifier trained with SVMSMOTE-ENC on the Insurance dataset.

Figure 4. Feature importance results from a Random Forest classifier trained with SMOTE-ENC on the Insurance dataset.

As illustrated in Figures 3 and 4, the two most important features identified by the Random Forest classifier on the insurance dataset are categorical variables. While these features dominate in both models, their combined contribution is higher in SMOTE-ENC ($\approx 75\%$) than in SVMSMOTE-ENC ($\approx 66\%$), indicating a stronger reliance on categorical predictors. In SVMSMOTE-ENC, feature importance is more evenly distributed across both numerical and categorical variables. Our proposed oversampler outperforms the baseline model SMOTE-ENC in terms of predictive performance and stability, achieving a higher mean F1-score and lower variance. Although both models exhibit comparable balanced accuracy, the improved F1-score and reduced standard deviation in SVMSMOTE-ENC suggest more robust generalization, which can be attributed to a more balanced feature contribution and the effectiveness of SVM-SMOTE in enhancing class boundary learning, as discussed in the previous section.

Evaluation on Credit Approval Datasets

Financial institutions are primarily interested in determining which consumers are most likely to default on loans. In credit risk assessment, sensitivity is defined as the proportion of actual defaulters correctly predicted as defaults, quantifies the detection of high-risk borrowers, whereas specificity, defined as the proportion of actual non-defaulters correctly predicted as non-defaults, quantifies the correct approval of low-risk borrowers. Balanced accuracy is defined as the arithmetic mean of sensitivity and specificity. SVMSMOTE-ENC achieved the

best performance across both datasets, whereas SMOTE-ENC demonstrated comparable results with only marginal differences.

Evaluation on Breast Cancer and Tic-Tac-Toe Datasets

Since both datasets consist solely of categorical features, G-SMOTENC and SMOTE-NC are not applicable. Among all datasets, the proposed oversampler achieved the highest balanced accuracy and F1-score gains on the Breast Cancer dataset, with improvements of 4.39 % and 4.05 %, respectively, compared to SMOTE-ENC.

6 Conclusion and Future Work

In this paper, we introduced SVMSMOTE-ENC, a novel enhancement to the SMOTE-ENC algorithm, to address the challenges of class imbalance in datasets with nominal and continuous features. In imbalanced classification tasks, conventional oversampling methods often fail to adequately select informative minority instances, leading to the generation of synthetic samples in less relevant regions. To address this limitation, SVMSMOTE-ENC leverages support vectors to identify critical borderline areas and generates synthetic samples in these regions, where they are most effective in shaping the decision boundary. Through extensive experimentation on six real-world datasets, we demonstrate that SVMSMOTE-ENC significantly improves the classification performance of a Random Forest classifier compared to SMOTE-ENC, G-SMOTENC and SMOTE-NC. Across multiple evaluation metrics, including F1-score and balanced accuracy, our approach outperforms existing methods. These results indicate that SVMSMOTE-ENC is an effective oversampling technique. The observed performance improvement is related to the boundary-focused selection mechanism, which identifies critical regions for synthetic data generation, together with its Chie-based encoding mechanism that captures the relationship between categorical features and the target variable. Future work may investigate the integration of efficient SVM-based mechanisms to improve its applicability to mixed-type datasets with a higher proportion of categorical features.

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